

Predicting Urban Expansion in Land Use in Chiang Mai Using a Multi-Layer Perceptron-Markov Chain Model

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Summary

Urban expansion, a pressing issue in many developing countries, is particularly challenging in Chiang Mai, a densely populated urban area in the Northern region facing expansion from its city center. Using Landsat images from 2007 to 2021 and demographic and economic data, this study identified factors driving land use changes. Employing the Multi-Layer Perceptron-Markov Chain (MLP-MC) model, the research achieved over 90% accuracy in modeling LULC and urban expansion. Applying MLP-MC to simulate 2037 projections revealed urban occupation on approximately half of Chiang Mai's land.

KEYWORDS: Urban Expansion, Land Use, Chiang Mai, Multi-Layer Perceptron, Markov Chain

1. Introduction

Over the past three decades, urban areas in developing nations have experienced a rapid surge in population growth. The 2014 revision of World Urbanization Prospects suggests recent urbanization trends focus on population shifts between urban and rural areas (United Nations, 2015). A global trend of converting land for urbanization and rural-to-urban migration is highlighted by reports, indicating about 53% of the world's population lived in urban areas in 2015, with 77% from developed countries and 48% from developing nations (Population Reference Bureau, 2015). This escalating urbanization is an ongoing trajectory, with projections indicating the global urban population will reach 5 billion by 2035, concentrated mainly in African and Asian countries (UN-HABITAT, 2015). This trajectory presents land use, economic dynamics, and environmental sustainability challenges, underscoring the need for comprehensive global urban planning.

Chiang Mai, the country's second-largest province by land area, exhibits diverse land uses. The urban and built-up area in Chiang Mai has consistently expanded, growing from 352,520 rai (4.84%) in 2007 to 441,578 rai (6.05%) in 2020 (Department of Land Development, 2010). The province's role as a hub for trade, services, tourism, industry, and transportation, coupled with its significance in tropical and temperate fruit cultivation, has fueled population growth, rising from 1,661,349 in 2007 to 1,784,370 in 2020. While this growth has positively impacted the province, fostering economic development and prosperity distribution, it has also led to spatial challenges like deforestation, air pollution, encroachment on agricultural land, and land-use conflicts negatively affecting local livelihoods.

In contemporary urban studies, analyzing land use and land cover (LULC) has become crucial for monitoring spatial and temporal patterns of urban expansion. Although satellite imagery has been widely used to understand the spatial-temporal evolution of urban areas, predicting future LULC requires integrating land use models (Losiri *et al.*, 2017). These models, rooted in urban morphology and dynamic LULC processes, forecast patterns and scales of urban expansion, encompassing empirical and statistical models, dynamic models, integrated models, and hybrid models. Affirmation models

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within these frameworks consider past changes during calibration and exhibit a sigmoidal pattern in the change potential function.

To understand the dynamics of urban expansion and LULC in Chiang Mai, this study integrates physical, demographic, and economic factors into the LULC model to calibrate and simulate future land use changes from the base year 2021. It employs multi-criteria evaluation and multilayer perception to identify driving factors through a land change model (LCM), simulating urban LULC in 2037.

2. Data and Methodology

This study employed four key processes to forecast urban expansion in Chiang Mai. The subsequent sections detail these processes.

2.1. Satellite Image Preparation and LULC Classification

Extracting LULC info from Landsat data involved obtaining multiple dates (2007, 2012, 2017, and 2021) from the USGS. After geometric correction, images were classified into five classes. Accuracy was assessed using the overall accuracy and Kappa coefficient.

2.2. Data Compilation for Urban LULC Modeling

Urban LULC modeling required diverse input data, including demographic and economic data, as well as geo-databases on topography, transportation, streams, and administrative boundaries. These were collected in various formats and scaled into raster format at 30-meter resolution.

2.3. Change Analysis

Historical changes in urban areas were analyzed by comparing LULC maps from different 3-time periods. Transitions between LULC states were identified through cross-tabulation analysis of differential times.

2.4. Urban LULC Modeling

2.4.1. Multi-Layer Perceptron-Markov Chain (MLP-MC)

This method predicts future LULC by combining MLP and MC in Land Change Modeler (LCM). The process includes change analysis, transition potential modeling, and LULC change prediction.

- **Change Analysis:** Identifies major transitions modeled separately.
- **Transition Potential Determination:** Uses Cramer's V to identify factors influencing conversion between LULC classes. Then, MLP uses the influent factors to generate a transition potential map for each LULC class.
- **LULC Change Prediction:** LCM uses change prediction to determine future LULC quality. This process uses the advantages of the Markov Chain model to generate LULC probability in each LULC and the multi-objective evaluation combines both probability and LULC transition potential to allocate the future LULC change

2.4.2. Model Validation and Application

Validation assesses simulated LULC results by comparing them with reference maps. The study used overall accuracy and the Kappa coefficient for this purpose. After assessing predicted LULC accuracy, the model was used to predict the future LULC in 2037.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 LULC Classification and Accuracy Assessment

The analysis involved using the maximum likelihood algorithm to study the LULC maps for the four years corresponding to Landsat images (2007, 2012, 2017, and 2021). Auxiliary datasets were incorporated to enhance the quality of these maps. The accuracy results from the image classification of all four maps were greater than 80 percent. Therefore, all the maps could be used for analysis. The classification results from the four LULC maps indicated that agricultural land dominated throughout the study period, but its proportion experienced a significant decrease. Conversely, urban land exhibited a continuous increase, driven by the demand for residential and industrial purposes. Miscellaneous land slightly fluctuated, while water and forest areas remained relatively consistent.

3.2 Change Analysis

This highlights that the most prominent change during the study period was the transformation from agriculture to urban land. The second significant transition observed was the shift from agriculture to miscellaneous land, as revealed in the analysis. The third notable change involved the conversion from miscellaneous to agriculture, identified through the change analysis with a rate of change lower than the second transition. Additionally, the transformation of miscellaneous land into urban land played a role in the overall LULC change. However, the change analysis also uncovered various transitions within each LULC class, influencing both urban growth and LULC alterations in Chiang Mai (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1 The amount of change in each period

3.3 Urban LULC Prediction

This study incorporated the MLP-MC approach within the conventional model to simulate and investigate urban LULC and expansion in Chiang Mai. The resulting simulated LULC maps for the three time periods—2012, 2017, and 2021—are presented in **Figure 2** and summarized in **Table 1**.

Figure 2 Comparison of LULC prediction and urban extend from Multi-Layer Perceptron-Markov Chain (MLP-MC): (a) 2012; (b) 2017; and (c) 2021

Table 1 Accuracy assessment of simulated LULC maps from the MLP-MC environments

Type	Year		
	2012	2017	2021
Overall accuracy	92.1738	90.5811	89.4969
K standard	0.9108	0.8979	0.8924
K no	0.9383	0.9257	0.9171
K locationStrata	0.9146	0.9298	0.9072

The application of the model aims to simulate the urban expansion of Chiang Mai province in 2037. The outcomes are visualized in **Figure 3** and summarized in **Table 2**.

Figure 3 LULC simulation maps in 2037

Table 2 The simulated area of LULC maps in 2037

LULC Classes	LULC in 2023	
	km	%
Agriculture	5,898.14	26.65
Water	283.70	1.28
Urban	1,014.32	4.58
Forest	14,572.69	65.83
Miscellaneous	367.06	1.66

4. Conclusion

In exploring future Land Use/Land Cover (LULC) dynamics and urban expansion, this study employed the Multi-Layer Perceptron-Markov Chain (MLP-MC) method to generate transition probabilities and rates for simulations. Validation of simulated results for the years 2007, 2012, and 2021 was conducted to determine the most effective prediction method. The accuracy assessments indicated that MLP-MC produced superior results. Consequently, the simulation for the year 2037 utilized MLP as the predictive platform.

The simulation reveals that urban and built-up areas constitute the primary LULC types, occupying approximately half of the land in Chiang Mai. Notably, a significant portion of agricultural land is projected to undergo conversion to urban or built-up areas unless appropriate measures are implemented. This study underscores the effectiveness of integrating LULC modeling approaches, remote sensing data, and driving factors for professionally simulating future LULC changes. Consequently, the spatial distribution, direction, and temporal aspects of urban expansion can be monitored. Access to such crucial information is imperative for planners and organizations to allocate infrastructure strategically and manage sustainable land use in response to the diverse needs of the population in this region.

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Biographies

Chudech Losiri, serving as an Assistant Professor at the Department of Geography within the Faculty of Social Sciences at Srinakharniwit University, shares expertise in geography and geoinformatics at various academic levels. His specialization lies in the utilization of remote sensing and land use modeling. His research focus predominantly revolves around monitoring urban expansion in Thailand.